

Trident™ Thermal Conductivity Application Highlight: Characterization of a Battery Pouch's Anisotropic Thermal Conductivity

This Application Highlight illustrates C-Therm's FLEX Transient Plane Source (TPS) system being utilized to investigate the anisotropic thermal conductivities of a lithium pouch battery cell using the Single-Sided Utility.

Battery cells emit heat as they discharge electricity. Improper thermal management in a battery system can lead to capacity degradation, reduced efficiency, accelerated aging, and, in extreme cases, catastrophic safety hazards such as thermal runaway¹. A comprehensive characterization of the battery's thermal properties, including thermal conductivity, is essential for successful thermal management.

Figure 1. Swollen Lithium Pouch Battery: One of the Consequences of Improper Thermal Management².

Due to the multilayered structure of batteries, their thermal-conductivity profiles are usually anisotropic; heat transfer in the through-plane (Z) direction is often overpowered by that in the in-plane (R) direction. The separation of these two thermal conductivity directionalities is made possible by C-Therm's FLEX TPS thermal conductivity sensor. It should be noted that the through-plane direction is influenced by thermal contact resistance between the cell layers. As such, mechanical pressure, surface roughness, etc., will directly influence the effective thermal conductivity.

Figure 2. C-Therm 13mm FLEX Transient Plane Source Thermal Conductivity Sensor.

¹ K. Maher, A. Boumaiza, and R. Amin, "Thermal management challenges in lithium-ion batteries: understanding heat generation mechanisms", Chemical Communications, Vol. 61, Issue 18, pp 3740-3743, Aug 2025

² Image Source: <https://www.stockwell.com/blog/designing-battery-pad-for-li-ion-pouch/>

The table below shows the results measured using the FLEX TPS sensor. The separated Z- and R-directional thermal conductivities differ by a large magnitude, possibly due to polymer material on the exterior inhibiting the Z-directional heat transfer, while the aluminum film within the casing is dominating the R-directional heat transfer. Separation of the two directions is made possible given the battery cell's RhoCp (Volumetric Heat Capacity) is known or can be determined.

Figure 3: Schematic diagram demonstrating the R- and Z- directional thermal conductivities.

Table 1: Measured results and calculated values for directional and bulk values

Single-Sided TPS Anisotropy (Wm ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)			Single-Sided TPS Bulk (Wm ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)
k _Z (Axial)	k _R (Radial)	k _{Z,R} (Calculated)	k _{Bulk} (Measured)
0.213	125	5.17	5.01

The geometric mean of the thermal conductivities in both Z- and R-directions was also calculated³ and compared against the values obtained using the bulk module. Two values were in close agreement with one another, with the mean value being significantly different from the radial and axial thermal conductivity values. This highlights the need for anisotropic separation when characterizing these materials, as the bulk value may not represent the true thermal conduction regime in the through- and in-plane directions.

³ The geometric mean was calculated using the formula: $k_{Z,R} = \sqrt{k_Z \cdot k_R}$

About Us:

C-Therm is the world leader in thermal conductivity instrumentation for test and measurement of polymers, ceramics, composites, insulation, textiles, and a wide range of other materials. Headquartered in Fredericton, New Brunswick, Canada, C-Therm specializes in non-destructive thermal analysis solutions that empower researchers, manufacturers, and quality control professionals across various industries – from aerospace and automotive to electronics and energy storage.

To learn more about C-Therm's Trident thermal conductivity instrument, visit
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